

**PHYTOSOME TECHNOLOGY: A NOVEL LIPID-BASED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM
FOR ENHANCED BIOAVAILABILITY OF HERBAL ACTIVES**Chandana S.*¹ Venkatesh¹, Mr. Raghu Kumar H. M.¹, Hanumanthachar K. Joshi²¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Sarada Vilas College of Pharmacy, Mysuru, Karnataka, India.²Department of Pharmacognosy, Sarada Vilas College of Pharmacy, Mysuru, Karnataka, India.***Corresponding Author: Chandana S.**

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ABSTRACT

Phytosome technology is a novel and patented drug delivery system developed to overcome the poor bioavailability of conventional herbal formulations. It involves the formation of lipid-compatible molecular complexes by chemically binding water-soluble phytoconstituents, such as flavonoids and polyphenols, with phospholipids, mainly phosphatidylcholine. This complexation enhances membrane permeability, stability, and systemic absorption of herbal actives compared to traditional extracts and liposomes. Phytosomes protect phytoconstituents from gastrointestinal degradation and significantly improve their pharmacokinetic and therapeutic performance. Various preparation techniques, including solvent evaporation, mechanical dispersion, salting-out, lyophilization, and anti-solvent precipitation, have been developed. Comprehensive evaluation using DSC, SEM, TEM, FTIR, particle size analysis, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency confirms their effectiveness. Owing to enhanced bioavailability, reduced dose requirement, hepatoprotective activity, safety, and wide pharmaceutical and cosmetic applicability, Phytosomes represent a promising platform in modern herbal drug delivery systems.

KEYWORDS: Phytosomes, Herbal drug delivery, Phosphatidylcholine, Bioavailability enhancement, Flavonoids, Novel drug delivery system (NDDS).**INTRODUCTION**

Phytosome technology was developed by Indena S.P.A., Italy.^[1] The term “*Phyto*” denotes plant, while “*some*” refers to a cell-like structure.^[2] Phytosomes are also known as herbosomes. This patented delivery system was developed to overcome the poor bioavailability associated with conventional herbal extracts.

Phytosome technology involves the complexation of standardized plant extracts or water-soluble phytoconstituents with phospholipids to form lipid-compatible molecular complexes. This approach significantly enhances the absorption and bioavailability of herbal drugs.^[3] Phytosomes represent an important advancement in novel drug delivery systems (NDDS), particularly for herbal and traditional medicines derived from plant sources.

Phytosomes are vesicular systems in which herbal drugs are incorporated into phospholipid complexes and are generally available in nano-sized form. Unlike liposomes, Phytosomes involve chemical bonding between the phytoconstituent and the phospholipid, resulting in improved stability and enhanced therapeutic efficacy.

Certain water-soluble Phytomolecules, mainly flavonoids and polyphenolic compounds, exhibit poor lipid solubility and limited absorption when administered orally. By reacting these phytoconstituents with phospholipids, lipid-friendly complexes known as Phytosomes are formed. These complexes exhibit improved membrane permeability, enabling better passage across lipid-rich biological membranes and enhanced systemic availability.^[4]

Phytosomes provide an envelope-like protective coating around the active constituents of herbal extracts. This protective layer shields the bioactive compounds from degradation caused by gastric secretions and intestinal bacteria.^[5]

The phospholipid component of Phytosomes facilitates efficient interaction with biological membranes, thereby improving drug absorption and bioavailability compared to conventional herbal formulations.

Various phospholipids are employed in the preparation of Phytosomes, including phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylserine, phosphatidylethanolamine, and phosphatidylinositol. Among these, phosphatidylcholine is the most widely used due to its additional therapeutic benefits.

Phosphatidylcholine exhibits hepatoprotective activity and is beneficial in the management of liver disorders such as alcoholic steatosis, drug-induced liver damage, and hepatitis. Additionally, phospholipids act as natural digestive aids and serve as effective carriers for both fat-soluble and water-soluble nutrients.^[6]

Standardized plant extracts, particularly flavonoids, are commonly formulated as Phytosomes due to their therapeutic potential and poor bioavailability in conventional dosage forms. Flavonoids selected for Phytosome formulation include compounds from the following groups.

Quercetin, Kaempferol, Quercetin-3-rhamnoglucoside, Quercetin-3-rhamnoside, Hyperoside, Vitexin, Diosmin, (+)-Catechin, (-)-Epicatechin, Apigenin-7-glucoside, Luteolin, Luteolin glucoside, Ginkgonetin, Isoginkgonetin, Bilobetin. These phytoconstituents show enhanced therapeutic efficacy when delivered as Phytosome complexes.

COMPARISON BETWEEN PHYTOSOME AND LIPOSOME^[9]

There is number of research has been carried out on Phytosomes which state that Phytosomes have good bioavailability, absorption, and excellent therapeutic efficacy over liposome. Comparison between Phytosomes and Liposomes is represented in Table 1 along with their structure in Figure. 1.

Fig. 1: Difference between Phytosome and Liposome.

Table 1: Comparison between Phytosomes and Liposomes.^[7-9]

Sr. No	Properties	Phytosome	Liposome
1.	Bonding	Associated with few molecules (mainly with Phospholipid and polyphenol extract)	Number of molecules and even they are not connected well
2.	Oral drug delivery	Best for oral delivery	connected well poor oral bioavailability.
3.	Phospholipid ratio	Preferably 1:1, 1:2 ratio is preferred for its preparation.	Lipid ration is increased up to 10 times than the chief active constituents

Properties of Phytosomes^[10,11]

Physicochemical Properties

- Phytosomes are molecular assemblies formed through the complexation of bioactive phytoconstituents with natural phospholipids. These complexes are produced by reacting defined ratios of phospholipids and active constituents in a suitable solvent.
- The association between the phospholipid and the phytoconstituent is mainly driven by hydrogen bond formation between the polar head groups of the phospholipid and the polar functional moieties of the active compounds.
- In aqueous environments, Phytosomes adopt a cell-like structure resembling Liposomes. However, unlike liposomes—where the active compounds are encapsulated within the aqueous core—in Phytosomes the phytoconstituents are chemically

linked to the phospholipid polar heads, forming an integral part of the membrane.

- Phytosomes consist of a small number of strongly bound molecular complexes, whereas liposomes are aggregates of numerous phospholipid molecules that encapsulate active constituents without forming specific molecular interactions.

Biological Properties

- Phytosome formulations significantly enhance the intestinal absorption of phytoconstituents and improve their systemic bioavailability upon oral administration.
- They represent an advanced herbal drug delivery system, demonstrating superior therapeutic performance compared to conventional herbal extracts.

- Phytosomes exhibit improved pharmacokinetic behaviour relative to unformulated herbal drugs.

Phytosome Technology

Phytosome technology is based on the ability of water-soluble phytoconstituents, such as flavonoids and terpenoids present in plant extracts, to form complexes with phosphatidylcholine. In this approach, a stoichiometric proportion of phosphatidylcholine is reacted with a standardized plant extract in a non-polar solvent system to facilitate complex formation.

Phosphatidylcholine is a bifunctional molecule comprising a hydrophilic choline moiety and a lipophilic phosphatidyl moiety. This dual nature plays a crucial role in enhancing the bioavailability of water-soluble phytoconstituents, particularly simple flavonoids. The hydrophilic choline group interacts with and binds the polar phytoconstituents, forming the core of the complex, while the lipophilic phosphatidyl moiety surrounds this core, imparting lipid compatibility to the system. The resulting structure is a lipid-compatible molecular complex known as a Phytosome.

The binding of phytoconstituents to the polar choline moiety of phosphatidylcholine occurs through chemical interactions, which can be characterized and confirmed using specific spectroscopic techniques such as FT-IR, NMR, and DSC.^[12,13]

Mechanism of Phytosome Technology

The poor absorption and low bioavailability of polyphenolic constituents are mainly attributed to two factors. First, these compounds possess multiple ring structures and relatively large molecular sizes, which limit their absorption through passive diffusion. Second, flavonoids and other polyphenolic constituents exhibit low lipid solubility, further restricting their passage across biological membranes. These limitations significantly hinder their effective absorption.

Phytosome technology addresses these challenges by forming complexes between polyphenols and phospholipids, typically in a 1:1 or 1:2 ratio. This complexation results in the formation of a phytosomal structure, in which the bioactive constituents are surrounded by a lipid layer, thereby enhancing their solubility, membrane permeability, and overall bioavailability.^[14]

Preparation of Phytosomes

Phytosomes are prepared by complexing phytoconstituents with phospholipids using various conventional and non-conventional techniques. The major methods employed for Phytosome preparation are described below.

1. Solvent Evaporation Method

In this method, phytoconstituents and phosphatidylcholine (PC) are dissolved together in an

organic solvent in a round-bottom flask. The reaction mixture is maintained at an optimum temperature, usually around 40 °C, for approximately 1 hour to achieve maximum drug entrapment. The organic solvent is then evaporated to form a thin film of Phytosomes. The dried film is passed through a 100-mesh sieve and stored overnight in a desiccator to ensure complete drying.^[15]

2. Mechanical Dispersion Method

In the mechanical dispersion method, lipids dissolved in an organic solvent are brought into contact with an aqueous phase containing the phytoconstituent. The organic solvent is subsequently removed under reduced pressure, leading to the formation of a Phytospholipid complex.

Recent advancements include the use of supercritical fluid (SCF) technologies such as the gas anti-solvent (GAS) technique, compressed anti-solvent process (PCA), and supercritical anti-solvent (SAS) method for the preparation of phospholipid complexes.^[16]

3. Salting-Out Technique

In this technique, both phosphatidylcholine and the plant extract are dissolved in a suitable organic solvent. A non-polar solvent such as n-hexane is then gradually added until precipitation of the extract-PC complex occurs. The precipitate is collected, dried, and stored appropriately.^[17]

4. Lyophilization Method

In the lyophilization method, DSN is completely dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to obtain a 2.5% w/v solution. This solution is added to a solution of soybean phosphatidylcholine (SPC) prepared in t-butyl alcohol (1.5% w/v). The mixture is stirred for 3 hours using a magnetic stirrer to allow complex formation. The resulting complex is isolated by freeze-drying.

After lyophilization, the DSN:SPC complex (yield approximately 90.4% w/w) is stored in a desiccator over phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅) at 4 °C until further evaluation. During formulation development, various parameters such as SPC type (Lipoid® S100, S75, and SPC-3), drug-to-phospholipid ratio (1:1, 1:2, and 1:4), and co-solvent type (methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetone, and t-butyl alcohol) are evaluated.^[18,19]

5. Anti-Solvent Precipitation Process

A measured quantity of herbal extract and phospholipids is refluxed with approximately 20 ml of an organic solvent such as acetone at temperatures below 50 °C for 2–3 hours. The reaction mixture is then concentrated to a volume of about 10 ml. Upon the addition of a low-polarity solvent like n-hexane with continuous stirring, Phytosome precipitates are formed. These precipitates are filtered, dried in a desiccator, pulverized, and stored in dark amber glass containers at controlled temperature.^[20]

6. Rotary Evaporation Process

In this method, a specific amount of herbal extract and phospholipids is dissolved in 30 ml of a water-miscible organic solvent such as acetone. The mixture is stirred for two hours at temperatures below 50 °C using a rotary evaporator. The solvent is evaporated to form a thin film, and an anti-solvent such as n-hexane may be added to induce precipitation. The obtained Phytosomes are stored in amber-coloured glass containers under controlled temperature and humidity conditions.^[21]

7. Ether Injection Method

Phospholipids dissolved in ether are slowly injected dropwise into a solution containing the phytoconstituents. Upon subsequent removal of the solvent, cellular vesicles are formed, resulting in the formation of Phytosome complexes.^[22]

Common steps in formulation of Phytosomes

Fig. 2 Preparation of Phytosomes.

Evaluation of Phytosomes^[23-25]

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry was employed to study the thermal behavior of the polyphenolic drug extract, phosphatidylcholine, their physical mixture, and the drug-phospholipid complex. Each sample was placed in an aluminium pan and heated over a temperature range

of 0–400 °C at a heating rate of 50–250 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM analysis was conducted to examine the surface morphology and particle size of the phytosomal complex. The dry sample was mounted on a brass stub and coated with gold using an ion sputter. The complex was randomly scanned at 100× magnification.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy was used to determine the size and structural characteristics of the phytosomal vesicles. Imaging was performed at 1000× magnification.

Drug Entrapment Efficiency and Loading Capacity

The phytosomal formulation was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 90 minutes at 4 °C to separate the entrapped Phytosomes from the free drug. The concentration of the untrapped drug in the supernatant was determined using UV spectroscopy. The percentage entrapment efficiency was calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Entrapment Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of free drug}}{\text{Weight of total drug}} \times 100$$

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

FTIR spectroscopy was performed to assess the structural integrity and chemical compatibility of the drug and phospholipid. The phytosomal formulation was triturated with potassium bromide and compressed into pellets under a pressure of 600 kg/cm². Spectral scanning was carried out over a wavelength range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

Particle Size Analysis and Zeta Potential

Particle size distribution and zeta potential of the phytosomal complex were measured using a Malvern Zeta sizer. An argon laser was employed for the characterization of particle size and surface charge.

In Vitro and *In Vivo* Evaluation

In vitro and *in vivo* studies were conducted based on the physicochemical properties of the drug and its major phytoconstituents complexed with phospholipids. Suitable animal models were selected depending on the therapeutic application of the phytosomal formulation.

Advantages of Phytosomes^[26-28]

1. Phospholipids, particularly phosphatidylcholine, serve a dual function in phytosomal formulations by acting both as a drug carrier and as a bioactive component with health benefits, such as hepatoprotective activity.
2. Phytosomes enhance the absorption of hydrophilic phytoconstituents, leading to improved therapeutic efficacy.
3. Increased efficacy allows for a reduction in the required dosage of the active constituent.

4. Phytosomal formulations exhibit improved physicochemical and chemical stability.
5. Due to the presence of a lipid layer surrounding the phytoconstituents, Phytosomes possess enhanced skin permeability, thereby increasing their effectiveness in topical applications.
6. Phosphatidylcholine used in formulating Phytosome process besides as a carrier also known as nourishes of the skin.

Disadvantages of Phytosomes^[29]

1. Despite their advantages, Phytosomes may undergo rapid release or exclusion of the incorporated phytoconstituents.
2. Certain phospholipids have been reported to promote cell proliferation in the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line.
3. A major limitation of Phytosomes is the possible leaching of phytoconstituents from the system, which can lead to a reduction in the intended drug concentration.

Applications of Phytosomes^[30]

1. Enhancement of the bioavailability of poorly absorbed phytoconstituents.
2. Delivery of large and structurally diverse molecules, such as peptides and proteins.
3. Use of safe and biocompatible components.
4. Hepatoprotective drug delivery systems.
5. Widely approved for cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications.
6. Low-risk formulation profile.
7. Well-documented toxicological properties.
8. High commercial and market potential.

CONCLUSION

Phytosome technology represents a significant advancement in the field of herbal drug delivery systems by effectively addressing the major limitation of poor bioavailability associated with conventional plant extracts. Through the formation of stable molecular complexes between phytoconstituents and phospholipids, particularly phosphatidylcholine, Phytosomes enhance membrane permeability, absorption, and therapeutic efficacy of water-soluble herbal compounds such as flavonoids and polyphenols. Unlike liposomes, the chemical bonding in Phytosomes provides superior stability and improved pharmacokinetic performance. Various preparation methods and characterization techniques further support their versatility and reliability as a novel drug delivery platform. In addition to improved bioavailability, Phytosomes offer added health benefits, including hepatoprotective activity, safety, and biocompatibility, making them suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and cosmetic applications. Despite certain limitations such as possible phytoconstituent leakage, Phytosomes demonstrate strong commercial potential and low-risk profiles. Overall, Phytosome technology offers a promising and effective approach for maximizing the therapeutic

potential of herbal medicines and represents a valuable strategy in modern drug delivery research.

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